

LEARNING THROUGH ACTION

THREE CYCLIC PHASES OF ENGAGING PROFESSIONAL LEARNING

Introduction

Learning Through Action is a practical and engaging **professional learning method** designed to help you grow as a teacher while making a meaningful impact in your classroom. It follows a simple cyclical process: you identify a problem, try out strategies to address it, reflect on what worked and what didn't, and then make adjustments for improvement. This cycle of planning, teaching, reflecting & revising transforms everyday teaching into opportunities for learning and growth. By using this method, you enhance your skills and inspire creativity, critical thinking, and problem-solving in your students. *Learning Through Action* emphasizes making meaningful changes step by step, all while fostering your professional learning along the way.

PLAN

1. **Identifying the problem:** Based on your observations and classroom experiences, identify a problem. This could be a topic you would like to develop about the classroom environment, instructional materials, classroom management, instructional methods, grading and evaluation etc.
2. **Gathering information:** It can be challenging to spot the problem at the beginning of a school year or semester, but the following may give you clues:
 - a. Gather information from your students through observation or conversation.
 - b. Gather information from the internet or other sources (teaching blogs/forums, articles, books etc.).
 - c. Gather information from PE teachers, other subject teachers or other stakeholders (parents, administrators etc.).
3. **Developing an Action Plan:** Fill in the boxes in the action plan template (see Appendix 1).

Developing a new action plan means that you will be doing something different in the future.

As a teacher, it's important to track your thoughts in a way that suits your style. Take time during the week to jot down ideas in a journal or planner, then reflect on what sparked them and any emerging patterns. Make time to share your notes with other teachers and discuss your observations. If your school doesn't provide space for this, work with your team to create one—it's worth it! Use these questions to guide your reflections: What's happening? Why is it happening? How can it improve?

Questions to Support Teachers

(Ask these questions to yourself or discuss with a colleague)

- What would I like to explore?
- What do my students need?
- What challenges am I facing in my teaching?
- Are there specific student groups (e.g., gender, ability level, cultural background) affected by this issue?
- Are there external factors (e.g., curriculum demands, school policies, resources) contributing to the problem?
- How does this problem affect my students' learning, engagement, or well-being?
- What evidence do I have that this is a problem (e.g., student behavior, grades, feedback)?
- What professional skills or knowledge I need to address this issue?
- Can this issue be addressed within the time and resources I have?
- What is one thing I would like to change?

TEACH

1. **Act your tasks:** Start implementing the tasks you have prepared in your action plan template (Appendix 1).
2. **Collect evidence:** Collect evidence from your students about the effectiveness of your practices through observations, surveys, open-ended questionnaires, interviews etc. (Appendix 2-3-4). You can also continue to receive feedback from another teacher(s) or other stakeholders whom you ask to observe your lesson.
3. **Analyze and interpret the evidence you have collected:** Gather student perspectives and analyze responses about your teaching.

You can always make revisions to your action plans for the purposes of improving teaching in subsequent cycles.

When working as a collaborative team, it is important to decide together what type of evidence will best help you to reach your goal. There are many ways to collect evidence, and it is also possible to use a mix of methods. You can gather information by surveying a large group of students, conducting interviews (one-on-one or in groups), observing what's happening in real-time, or analyzing documents like reports, lesson plans, or student works. Choose the methods that fit your question and help you get a clear picture of what's going on.

When analyzing student responses, start by reviewing your notes and capturing your initial impressions. Organize your thoughts into a rough draft framework, and be systematic, organized, honest, and careful in your approach. If possible, discuss your results with your fellow teachers to develop your ideas.

REFLECT & REVISE

- 1. Reflecting on the process:** To reflect on your findings, consider the following questions:
 - a. What? (What did I/we find?)
 - b. So what? (What do these findings mean?)
 - c. Now what? (What should we do after we make sense of the findings?)
- 2. Share your results with stakeholders** (PE teachers, parents, administrators, and other subject teachers - if necessary).
- 3. Re-planning a new action plan:** Try to answer the following question and re-plan your action plan: **“Based on what I have learned from this process, what should I do now?”**

By discussing your findings with administrators and colleagues, you can exchange ideas to enhance your practice. Furthermore, sharing your findings with students' parents can also foster collaboration and support for improved outcomes in the future. Talk to your students about your study and what you learned leading to new strategies that improve their learning and enhance the classroom environment.

Your work is to find meaning in your findings. They matter only when you interpret them. When you share your results, explain why you did the work, what you learned, and how these insights can help with future planning. Analyzing your findings carefully will help you make important changes in your practice.

Remember: This process repeats itself in a cycle: you plan, teach, and reflect & revise. After you analyze what you found and make changes, you start the cycle again. You use new insights to improve your teaching. Each cycle builds on the last one, leading to continuous growth in your skills and better learning outcomes for your students.

Action Plan Template

GOALS

(Specify your goal(s))

Define your goals for solving the problem you identified based on your observations and classroom experiences.

TASKS

(List necessary tasks to achieve your goal)

List the tasks you need to solve the problem you identified based on your observations and classroom experiences.

TIME PLAN

(Your timeline to complete your tasks)

Indicate the specific time or time frame you plan to resolve this issue.

RESOURCES

(Resources and people needed to help with the action plan)

Identify specific resources and people you can contact for support to resolve this issue.

DESIRED OUTCOMES

(Possible outcomes of your tasks)

Clarify what change or improvement you would like to see after your action plan and how this issue and your actions could benefit your students or colleagues in the long term.

Appendix 2. An example of open-ended questionnaire

Physical Activity Self-Assessment Exercise

This self-assessment exercise will help you better understand your skills, interests, abilities, and level of effort.

Do you feel physically fit? Explain why and why not.

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Which physical activities are you good at (such as those requiring endurance, speed, strength, or flexibility)?

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What is your favourite physical activity(s)?

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What is your least favorite physical activity(s)?

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STUDENTS RECOGNITION FORM

name:

Where did you get your information about physical activity and health?

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From which sources do you get information about physical activity and health?
(For example: school lessons, internet, books, etc.)

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Appendix 4. An example of physical activity record chart

Physical Activity Record Chart

Days	Physical activities performed (name)	Duration(min)	Intensity (Mild-Moderate-Severe)	Comment
Monday				
Tuesday				
Wednesday				
Thursday				
Friday				
Saturday				
Sunday				